

The Effect of Organizational Culture, Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

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Abstract: The study was conducted aimed at analyzing the influence of organizational culture on work motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment on employee performance. The research method with a survey approach, population, and sample number of respondents as many as 83 respondents with the technique of sampling simple random sampling with the formula Slovin. Analysis of multiple linear regression data with SPSS software version. 20. H1 research results: accepted influence of organizational culture sig. $0.022 < 0.05$ and $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ ($2,342 > 1,990$). H2: accepted the influence of work motivation on employee performance sig. $0,000 < 0.05$ and $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ ($3,792 > 1,990$). H3: rejected the effect of Job satisfaction on employee performance sig. $0.278 > 0.05$ and $t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$ ($1,093 < 1,990$). H4: the effect of organizational commitment is accepted on employee performance sig. $0.045 < 0.05$ and $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ ($2.093 > 1.990$). H5: simultaneous influence of X1, X2, X3, and X4 on the performance of employees sig. $0,000 < 0.05$ and $f \text{ count} > f \text{ table}$ ($40154 > 2.49$).

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment Employee Performance.

I. Introduction

Human resources become an important asset for companies, the existence of resources human beings or employees determine the success of the company. Company performance determined by how the employee's performance itself. An organizational culture which is the values created are understood and carried out consistently, in every organizational culture companies differ from one another so that it becomes the hallmark of a company and becomes a distinguishing organization from one another. The most human resources valuable, and behavioral science, many techniques and programs that can guide the utilization of human resources more effectively (Pertiwi & Oka Suryadinata Gorda, 2019) (Febriantina et al., 2018) (Fauzan & Sumiyati, 2015).

Organizational culture makes the company has a competitive advantage. Culture the company is a distinguishing feature with other organizations, therefore the company should be able to seriously implement the culture that is owned within realize employee performance (Febriantina et al., 2018). Organizational culture is decisive for the greatest increase in performance (Meutia, 2019). But organizational culture should be supported by work motivation to improve employee performance because of organizational culture still small contribution to the company that is equal to 23.9%, therefore, requires work motivation as one of the determining factors (Nelfianti et al., 2018) (Indayati et al., 2012).

II. Literature Review

Organizational culture influences employee job satisfaction, organizational culture describes a situation where employees can work with the rules binding which is called corporate culture, so that with organizational culture make values and principles in running the organization (Sugiyarti, 2012).

Motivation must work in a person to carry out and move someone is working in an institution or organization in achieving Hasibuan's maximum performance in (Simanjuntak, 2020) further Robbins stated motivation contained in

every person as a driver in realizing behavior to achieve what is expected. Because motivation is a condition where people won't make every effort for the organization and the interests of the individual itself (Simanjuntak, 2020).

If the motivation of employees is high then it will lead to maximum performance, but if conversely, the performance is not following the expectations of the company itself. Without motivation company work will have difficulty in achieving maximum goals, motivation causes everyone to work diligently and diligently. Someone's motivation can come from inside or outside. Work motivation arises because there is a need, because of money, awards known as extrinsic and intrinsic factors (Budi, et al., 2019).

Job satisfaction is a feeling that someone has in response to the environment existing to encourage someone and move and direct behavior to achieve the goal (Pertiwi & Oka Suryadinata Gorda, 2019). Job satisfaction becomes a determinant of company success. Job satisfaction is a matter of Personally, people will not be the same in terms of job satisfaction. Satisfaction is a picture the state of a person for a happy or unhappy attitude, satisfied or not at work, Satisfied employees will do their job happily and seriously but if the employee is not satisfied it will do the job as it is without trying to do good and many mistakes will occur (Tanjung, 2020).

So that employee job satisfaction can be realized it is necessary to consider the variables that determine, among others, organizational work motivation, if the company can be modulated and employees can receive well, it can create job satisfaction because job satisfaction is very difficult to achieve, job satisfaction is what is felt by all employees depend on the surrounding environment (Rismayadi & Maemunah, 2016).

Organizational commitment from employees is one of the determinants of a company's success. Organizational commitment means employees have a strong determination and are directly involved in advancing the company and want to always stay in the company because they have confidence and trust in the goals of the Gibson and Mathis organization (Sudirjo & Pawiyatan, 2006). People who do not commit will be seen from the attitude that they feel are not part of the organization, think of themselves as outsiders so they do not want to involve themselves totally in the organization. Ganesan and Weitz (1996) state that organizational commitment will look as characteristic as follows: 1. Feelings of having an organization 2. Having a sense of pride in the organization 3. Having a concern for the organization 4. Having a strong desire to work in the organization 5. Having a strong belief in organizational values and 6. Have a strong determination and act in the interests of the organization (Indayati et al., 2012).

Organizational commitment according to Luthans (2006) a loyal attitude of employees in the company where they work is a high sense of care and the desire to succeed and advance the organization not only for now but also for the future. Furthermore, indicators of organizational commitment consist of affective commitment, ongoing commitment, and normative commitment (Hafid, 2019), (Hakim & Hadipapo, 2015) (Nurraeda, Sruati, 2020).

Sedarmayanti (2009) states that performance is the achievement of an individual or group based on the duties and authority given by the organization, carried out by complying with all applicable rules, meaning that to produce performance must be done in good ways and there are no violations (Nelfianti et al., 2018).

Employee performance is a measure of company success, one of which is the performance of employees running the organization culture consistently, but employees must have motivation at work (Sugiyarti, 2012). Furthermore, performance is not only influenced by culture but there are also other factors such as salary, salary being a motivation that affects employee performance. Employee performance can be influenced by organizational development and organizational commitment, therefore it must create motivation in employees and job satisfaction.

There is a gap of previous research that examines organizational culture does not affect employee performance such as (Sriekaningsih, 2017), (Haryanti Shinta, 2015), (Megantara et al., 2019). Work motivation does not affect employee performance (Budi et al., 2019) (Dewi Shanty, 2017), (Hasmalawati, 2018) and job satisfaction does not affect employee performance (Tarjo, 2019b). While organizational commitment has no significant effect on employee performance (Dewi Shanty, 2017), (Murty & Hudiwinarsih, 2012) (Dewi, 2019).

The results of previous studies have discussed a lot about the influence of organizational culture, work motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment to employee performance, but there are still differences between the researchers mentioned above, so this study aims to confirm the gap of previous research results.

III. Methodology

The research used was a survey method, data collection using a questionnaire prepared in advance and distributed to respondents. Data sources consist of primary data and secondary data, primary research data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data from books and scientific journals. The study population was all employees and the study sample was 83 respondents who were determined using the Slovin formula and sampling techniques with simple random sampling. Analysis of research data using multiple linear regression with IBM Statistics SPSS version software. 20 (Tarjo, 2019).

Based on the research gap stated above and the literature review, the conceptual framework of this study is shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Research Concept Framework

Based on the framework of the concept of research in the picture. 1 above, the hypothesis in research as follows:

- H1 : Is there an influence of organizational culture on employee performance.
- H2 : Is there an influence of Work Motivation on employee performance
- H3 : Is there an effect of job satisfaction on employee performance
- H4 : Is there an influence of job satisfaction on employee performance
- H5 : Is there an influence of organizational culture work motivation job satisfaction and organizational commitment to employee performance

IV. Results

The research findings are presented in Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3 below:

Table. 1 Statistical test results T (Partial Test results)
Coefficients

	Variable	T	Sig.
1.	Culture Organization	2.342	.022
2.	Work Motivation	3.792	.000
3.	Satisfaction Work	1.093	.278
4.	Comitment Organization	2.039	.045

Based on Table 1 above, the coefficient value is 0.173, with a significant of $0.022 < 0.05$. The results of this test prove that organizational culture influences employee performance. The coefficient value is 0.661 with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$ means work motivation influences employee performance while the value of the coefficient 0.212 and significant

0.045 < 0.05 which means organizational commitment influences employee performance. Next, the F statistical test results (simultaneously) look like in Table 2 below:

Table 2 statistical F test results (Simultaneous Test results) Anova

Variable		F	Sig.
1	X1, X2, X3 dan X4	2.342	.000

Table 3. R square Test Results (R²) Model Summary^b

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.820 ^a	.673	3.470

Based on the results of the statistical tests in Table 3 the R Square value is 0.673. Value 0.673 x 100% = 67.3%. This means that the model used in the study of cultural variables organization, work motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment can predict and explain the effect on employee performance.

H1: There is an Effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

H1 statistical test results: accepted, note that t count > t table (2,342 > 1,990) and significance 0,000 < 0.05. This means that organizational culture has a significant effect on employee performance. An organizational culture which is an embedded value in employees contributes to improving employee performance.

Improved employee performance because employees have different ways of working, it means that the company's values are well understood and run continuously so that work by the rules set by the company has become habits, rooted even employees do not need to be watched they will work accordingly their respective duties, not because there are employees' employees working well, more because of his sense of responsibility towards work.

The results of this study support research conducted by (Febriantina, 2018), (Hafid, 2018), (Indayati, 2012), (Muzaki, 2017), (Rismayadi, 2019), (Sriekaningsih, 2018), (Nelfianti, 2018) and (Meutia, 2019) that organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. Because the existing organizational culture can be responded positively and be a consequence if you join the company, then run the prevailing cultural values. But the results of this study differ from studies conducted by (Haryani, 2019), (Ilma Megantara, 2019) that organizational culture does not significantly influence employee performance. This means that the culture that exists in the company has not been run well by all employees.

H2: There is an Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

H2 statistical test results: accepted, note that t count > t table (3,792 > 1,990) and significance of 0,000 < 0.05. This means that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Employees who have work motivation in someone will result in better performance or performance will increase.

Work motivation is a very important thing that must be owned by employees, employees who work well motivation will carry out their duties wholeheartedly, employees are also more disciplined, employees who have motivation can be caused by several things such as salaries, good employee relations even relations with superiors can be said to be harmonious. The results of this study support research conducted by (Dewi.N.N, 2019), (Murti, 2012), (Muzaki, 2019), (Pertwi, 2019), (Rismayadi, 2016) and (Simanjuntak, 2020).

But the results of this study are different from the results of research conducted by (Budi, 2019), (Hasmalawati, 2018) and (Dewi Shanti, 2017) that work motivation has no significant effect. This can be caused by many things including salary, reward, social relations, or family factors on the employee itself.

H3: There is an Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

H3 statistical test results: Rejected, it is known that the t value $< t$ table ($1,093 < 1,990$) and significance of $0.000 > 0.05$. This means that job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on the performance of the employee. Job satisfaction is a feeling that is owned by someone above the existing environmental response. Job satisfaction will be created can be their work, less challenging jobs, or high-risk jobs employees are not able to carry out well. The results of this study are in line with research conducted (Tarjo, 2019) that job satisfaction has no significant effect on employee performance. This means that employees feel that their work is less challenging or lacking supervision from superiors so that stressed employees face problems arising from their work.

However, the results of this study are not in line with research conducted by (Dewi, 2019), (Simanjuntak, 2020), (Sugiyarti, 2012) and (Tanjung, 2020) that job satisfaction can be realized by work by the capacity and ability of the employee alone. So employee job satisfaction is mainly due to the job itself, meaning employees feel there is a match with the task at hand. Employees who have a level of perceived satisfaction will have a good impact on performance. Satisfied employees will work optimally to achieve organizational goals is determined by how well the individual's performance has been achieved.

H4: There is an Influence of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

H4 statistical test results: accepted, it is known that the value of t count $> t$ table ($2,039 > 1,990$) and a significance of $0,000 < 0.05$. This means that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Organizational commitment indicates that employees have a strong determination to advance the company where they work. This employee commitment is an illustration that employees have a sense of belonging to the company, including the good, employees want to stay in the company and there is no desire to move to another company.

The results of this study support research conducted by (Murti, 2012), (Indayati, 2012), (Fauzan, 2015), (Dewi Shanti, 2017), (Hafid, 2019), (Meutia, 2019) that organizational commitment has a positive influence and significant to employee performance. Employee employment will be determined by how much the employee is determined to advance the company. The success of the company will be determined by how strong the employee's determination to stay afloat, the stronger the employee to stay in the long term for the sake of the sustainability of the organization, it will affect performance, but if employees who have the character of a jumping fleet then they will work if they see the benefits to be gained instead because the company is developing and going forward.

The results of this study differ from the results of research conducted by (Dewi.N.N, 2019), (Murti, 2012), and (Dewi Shanti, 2017) that organizational commitment has no significant effect on employee performance. This means that employees do not have a strong will to advance the company, employees who are not committed are also caused by low levels of job satisfaction and motivation. Low commitment to employees can be caused by employee perceptions. Employees feel that they are not part of the company so they feel strange, if employees have such thoughts, it will be difficult to create commitment in employees. If you feel like an outsider, then in their minds at work do not give all their abilities totally to the company.

H5: There is an Influence of Organizational Culture, Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction, and Commitment Organization of employee performance.

H5 statistical test results: accepted, it is known that the value of f count $> f$ table ($40.154 > 2.49$) and the significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that organizational culture, work motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment significantly influence employee performance. The results of this test together have a positive and significant effect.

So employees who understand well the organizational culture in which the company works have been run and accepted as a different value compared to other companies and feel proud to work at the company. With the company culture that they positively respond to, it becomes one of the motivations in employees. Work motivation will be created if the existing culture becomes its attraction, culture provides an opportunity to express creative ideas. Employee job satisfaction can be felt because they have income in the form of salary, good relations between employees and superiors, and also feel what is received so far by the expectations of the employees themselves.

Organizational commitment is manifested that employees want to work longer and provide the best for the company, organizational commitment occurs if the company is consistent with employees something that is promised will give a

strong determination in working must be better and better. So that these three independent variables together can positively and significantly influence employee performance.

V. Conclusion

H1 statistical test results: accepted, Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. H2: accepted, Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. H3 statistical test: rejected, job satisfaction has no significant effect on employee performance. H4 statistical test results: received, the commitment of the Organization has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. And H5: accepted, Organizational Culture, Work motivation, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Suggestions to management to improve employee job satisfaction can be through those related to the work whether it has been appropriately placed. Work or division of work weakens employee job satisfaction, this can happen because the work is less challenging or the work feels heavy by the employee. The next researcher can add work environment variables, leadership style, and competence.

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